

Genital herpes and homœopathy

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Summary

The aetiology, pathogenesis and clinical features of genital herpes are described. One patient with primary infection and another with recurrent herpes were treated with homœopathic remedies. It is observed that *Rhus tox.* alleviates the clinical features of genital herpes and if given early may prevent recurring illness. Recurring herpes may be treatable with a constitutional remedy.

Introduction

In recent years an increase in the incidence of genital herpes has been observed. This disease affects both the sexes. The clinical features were first described in France, in the eighteenth century, by a physician called Astruc.

First illness

Genital herpes is caused by the herpes simplex virus. The responsible infective virus is usually of type two (HSV2). Less commonly it is of type one (HSV1). The infection is acquired from a person with herpetic local lesions, through sexual contact, which may be genital or oro-genital. A person who has not suffered from facial herpes in the past and therefore does not have antibodies to HSV1, is more prone to develop genital herpes. Following the incubation period, the infected person complains of aches and pains, itching and burning sensations. Soon a group of vesicles appear and the adjacent skin is erythematous. Lymph glands in the inguinal regions are enlarged and tender. Later vesicles rupture, leaving shallow ulcers. Crusts are formed over the ulcers which subsequently heal. From these skin lesions, the virus is excreted for a few days. In both the sexes, the external genitalia, perianal region and perineum may be affected.

Dormant state

From the primary site of an infection, the viruses ascend along the peripheral nerves. They lie dormant in the dorsal ganglia.

Subsequent illness

The latent viruses may become active in febrile conditions, during menstruation, after an injury, or on exposure to ultraviolet light. If reactivated, the viruses descend along the peripheral nerves which are irritated. The patient experiences itching and burning sensations. Subsequently, herpetic lesions appear on the skin. Viruses are shed even in the absence of visible skin lesions.

A patient with a primary infection

A 25-year-old unmarried girl was seen on 20 May 1983, with a history of smarting of the vulva and perianal region for the previous three days. She had noticed painful swelling in the groins. On physical examination a few small vesicles and many shallow ulcers were noticed in the vulva, around the anus and in the left groin. Bean-sized lymph nodes were palpable in both inguinal regions. These lymph glands were tender. Laboratory investigations confirmed a clinical diagnosis of genital herpes.

The patient was advised to take *Rhus tox.* 30c, orally, three times a day and use Calendula locally. She was reviewed three weeks later when she did not complain of any symptoms. To date, she has not had a recurrence of genital herpes.

A patient with recurring illness

Another 25-year-old unmarried girl attended the homœopathic clinic on 29 May 1984, with the history that fourteen months earlier, in March 1983, she contacted HSV2 infection. Since then she had suffered from frequent attacks of genital herpes. During each attack she had developed vesicles and ulcers in the vulva and also in the perianal region. At every recurrence of her illness she was uncomfortable because of itching and tingling sensation in the affected areas. She was restless, depressed and had suicidal thoughts. She was neat, tidy, methodical and fastidious. She was prescribed a single dose of her constitutional remedy, *Arsen. alb.*, at a high potency of 10M. She was given a supply of *Rhus tox.* 6x. She took *Rhus tox.* three times a day for four weeks. With the above treatment, this patient improved. Three months later, she had a recurrence of minor symptoms. Therefore *Arsen. alb.* and *Rhus tox.* were repeated.

Discussion

Successful treatment of a disease means curing the present episode and also preventing the future recurrence of an illness. The immediate effect of *Rhus tox.* on genital herpes is significant. Proving of this remedy produces the following skin lesions. There are small vesicles surrounded by erythema. These vesicles may rupture, leaving shallow ulcers. There may be secondary infection of the skin lesions and enlargement of regional lymph nodes. Itching and burning sensations may be present. These local manifestations of *Rhus tox.* proving were recorded also in the above two patients who suffered from genital herpes and who responded well to the treatment with *Rhus tox.* A prompt use of this remedy in the primary infection may prevent the recurrence of the disease. This is observed in the first patient who continues to remain free from this illness after the initial symptoms in May 1983. It is possible that the early use of *Rhus tox.* in this disease might destroy the virus or somehow prevent it from ascending along the peripheral nerve to the dorsal ganglia.

Mental features of restlessness, depression and suicidal thoughts recorded by *Rhus tox.* provers were seen in the second patient who recovered from these symptoms with the use of the same remedy.

Only paralytic conditions caused by changes in the fibrous sheaths of the nerves can be treated with *Rhus tox.* *Rhus tox.* does not have any other effect on nervous

tissue. It is improbable that this remedy will act on the latent viruses in the dorsal ganglia and prevent recurrence of herpes. It will only alleviate local symptoms in recurrent herpes. This beneficial effect alone suggests administration of *Rhus tox.* in chronic herpes infection, probably for a prolonged period in a high potency.

Theoretically, a constitutional remedy should eliminate the virus from the dorsal ganglia. The second patient has not been able to get rid of the recurrent infection with her constitutional remedy *Arsenicum*. But because she feels very well with this homœopathic treatment, it appears that her vital force has been stimulated and she may one day be free from the recurrent genital herpes.